

A Blockchain and Cryptocurrency – A Case Study

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ABSTRACT

The money and finance world is changing right in front of our eyes. The technological weapon of choice driving the success of Bitcoin and other cryptocurrencies, a decentralized transaction and data management in short known as Blockchain. Blockchain has a ledger that contains a transaction spreadsheet. When someone trades or mines cryptocurrency, the transaction is recorded in a spreadsheet, which is referred to as a ledger in the virtual world. Blockchain technology gives up new possibilities for making data use more efficient and equitable. The amount of money invested in virtual currency over the last several years appears to have leveled off recently. This does not, however, suggest that blockchain technology, which underpins virtual currencies, has lost its utility. The increasing valuation of digital currencies provides a variety of problems and difficulties for the financial and political system. Almost majority of recent Blockchain-Based studies are focused on its application for cryptocurrencies such as Bitcoin, with just a limited number of studies exploring the use of Blockchain Technology in other fields. On the contrary, a new generation of blockchains, as well as associated applications, is currently being developed and deployed. Although there are over 1000 cryptocurrencies on the market, Bitcoin is the most well-known and commonly bought cryptocurrency on the planet. Bitcoin has a market capitalization of little over 725 billion dollars. Bitcoin, the first decentralized cryptocurrency, became live in January 2009 and was created by Satoshi Nakamoto whose identity is unknown. He has given the world something innovative, and it is up to the users to decide what they will do with it. The future of blockchain technology is very exciting; new technologies are continuously hitting the market, offering greater and bolder applications. The purpose of this paper is to provide a brief introduction to these topics. This white paper will give you an overview of how the KYC procedure could be carried on in a smooth flow with less time and cost consumption, which becomes a solution to many challenges like inconsistency in the verification process, security issues, and redundant work carried on by the Banks and other Financial Institutions.

Keywords— Blockchain, Cryptocurrency, Bitcoin, Future, Challenges, Security.

1. INTRODUCTION

Bitcoin and blockchain technology have started to define and shape new areas of computer science and information technology. The need for a decentralized currency has been used more as a theoretical concept, but it has become a reality in the last decade, owing to Satoshi Nakamoto's renowned paper in 2008, which introduced Bitcoin and blockchain technology. A

blockchain is a decentralized ledger that is created on the Internet by an infinite number of individuals. A ledger is a permanent record book. The record must be accurate and untampered with. It is a collection of files that contain whatever information needs to be preserved indefinitely. A basic blockchain is a series of files linked together to form a chain. Innovative financial channels, tools, and systems are ushering in new financial transaction paradigms and constructing alternative capital conduits.

2. BLOCKCHAIN : [1]

Blockchain is a method of storing data in such a way that it is difficult or impossible to alter, hack, or cheat it. A person in control of most regular databases, such as a SQL database, can make changes to the entries. Blockchain is unique in that no one is in charge; instead, the individuals who utilize it run it.

2.1 Blockchain Architecture

Like a traditional public ledger, a blockchain is a series of blocks that carry a comprehensive list of transaction data.

Fig 1: Blockchain Architecture

Block

It contains transaction-related information, such as when a transaction between two parties occurred, the date and time of the transaction, and the amount moved between the two dealing parties. The block header and the block body make up a block.

Digital Signature

It has a unique digital signature that is assigned to each individual who is a part of the network as a whole. This digital signature is used to identify which users engaged in the transaction at the moment of the transaction. Each block has a capacity of roughly 1 megabyte, which means that each block can store thousands of transactions.

2.2 Key Characteristics of Blockchain

Decentralization

Each transaction must be verified by a centrally trusted organization. Anyone can engage in a decentralized network and transact on the ledger. As a result, procedures are required to address the vulnerabilities that develop as a result of this design, as well as to verify that transactions are completed correctly. As a means of constructing computer networks, distributed computing has evolved. Blockchain is a technology that creates a decentralized ledger-based on distributed computing. To construct a decentralized ledger, a completely new algorithm must be devised, and this work resulted in the invention of Bitcoin.

Anonymity

Each user can communicate with the Blockchain with a created address, which does not expose the real identity of the user. Due to the inherent limitations of blockchain, it cannot ensure absolute privacy protection.

3. CRYPTOCURRENCY :

Digital currency which is known as Cryptocurrency is transferred between Blockchain users without the use of a middleman, which in most situations is a bank that used to be a backbone of the economic system. Cryptocurrency is just another sort of data that may be stored on the Blockchain. These transactions are kept on Blockchain, a distributed ledger system that is housed on computers all around the world. Cryptocurrencies are exchanged on cryptocurrency exchanges in the same way that stocks are exchanged on stock markets. A cryptocurrency wallet is a digital wallet that may be used to accept, store, and send digital currencies.

3.1 Most Popular Cryptocurrency [2,3]

Bitcoin

Satoshi Nakamoto's renowned paper in 2008 introduced the first decentralized cryptocurrency, Bitcoin in January 2009. Bitcoin is the world's most well-known and commonly utilized cryptocurrency. Bitcoin's current market capitalization is just over \$725 billion. Bitcoin has been bought by millions of people in the world, which has led several industries and organizations to make it a currency of exchange. Bitcoin has seen several rises and dips due to trading going on in the crypto market. If a group of people buys a certain amount of bitcoin at a particular time, the price increases, and if a group of people sells their bitcoin at a particular time price dump.

Ethereum [4]

Ethereum is the world's second well-known cryptocurrency and holds second place in Market Cap. Both Ethereum (ETH) and Bitcoin (BTC) have a lot in common. Above all, both ETH and BTC are based on the blockchain network. This is part of the cryptocurrency's worth, as well as what offers the security required to handle the digital currency.

3.2 Features of cryptocurrency [5]

Efficient

There is no need for a central authority or third-party intermediaries to handle and validate transactions when using a peer-to-peer database. The decentralized system allows users to interact and exchange cryptocurrencies directly with one another, with each transaction being confirmed on the blockchain. This means that anyone with access to the internet may instantly swap valuables anywhere in the world.

Trust-less

Cryptocurrency, such as Bitcoin, Ethereum, Doge allows for a trust-less transaction system. The network's decentralized nature means that no one has to trust anyone else for it to function. Any transaction between users can be validated by the blockchain. When a user broadcasts a Bitcoin transaction, all nodes receive it and verify the digital signatures before recording it on the blockchain. The nodes will discard the transaction if the signatures are invalid.

3.3 Cryptocurrency Development

Over time, it has been seen that cryptocurrencies, particularly Bitcoin, have been extremely volatile and component. This volatility is mostly determined by the decisions made by governments and financial regulators in specific countries regarding the use of cryptocurrency. Because people believe cryptocurrency is money and everything else is credit, cryptocurrency is growing faster than the internet. As a result, bitcoin has a large store of value.

People have been brought together by the invention and spread of the internet, and they may now communicate with one another. It is simple to share ideas around the world thanks to the internet. The rise of cryptocurrencies has been aided by digitalization.

3.4 The Causes of Cryptocurrency Price to rising [2]

Holding

A large portion of bitcoin is held or channeled by most cryptocurrency investors into private speculative reserves or investment vehicles. This increases the seeming shortage of cryptocurrency, effectively keeps cryptocurrencies unsuitable for public use, and prompts cost escalation as rising demand for bitcoin's limited flexibility rises unit costs.

Media Hype

Increased purchasing pressure and a spike in the price of cryptocurrencies can be caused by media hype. While media attention tends to raise prices, if prices climb too quickly, a bubble forms, which finally bursts and collapses the market. For Example, DogeCoin which had gained a lot of attention during March and April 2021 because the entrepreneur and business magnate, who is the founder, CEO, and chief engineer at SpaceX "Elon Musk" tweeted about Doge.

Adoption

When major stores and investors accept cryptocurrency, it has the potential to drive the price up. Important financial products, which allow large entities such as banks to invest in Cryptocurrency without actually purchasing it, are another major price driver.

Security [6]

Digital currencies claim to make saving, spending and transferring "digital money" safe, quick, and free of taxes, exchange rates, and government regulations. The cornerstone to blockchain's security is that any modifications to the database are instantaneously broadcast to all users, resulting in a safe, permanent record. Even if some users are hacked, the total database remains safe because copies of the data are in everyone's hands. On three levels, blockchains can improve security:

Identity theft prevention, Protection against tampering with data, and critical infrastructure protection. Blockchains are emerging as top contenders for resolving a variety of cybersecurity concerns and providing end-to-end protection to global organizations as more viable implementations of the technology are identified.

3.5 Challenges in accepting cryptocurrency as money [3,7]

Inadequate Legislation

Cryptocurrency is digital, and our authorities are unprepared to deal with such sophisticated technology. As a result, the lack of law governing digital currencies and ensuring any form of user safety has become a significant concern. The most important step in reducing the risk is to educate and teach individuals about the need of protecting their personal information.

Legal Obstacles

Another major stumbling block for bitcoin owners and users is the inability to spend their holdings. Bitcoin has become extremely scandalous in some nations due to its untraceable nature and negative image as a form of finance for massive illegal operations such as terrorist acts and the drug trade.

Cryptocurrency is currently experiencing a time of abrupt standstill, with little activity surrounding the technology. As a result, it's impossible to predict what the future holds unless widespread acceptance alters the legal barriers to crypto-trading.

Interoperability

Blockchain's capacity to connect, as well as computer system software's ability to share and utilize information, is a challenge. Separate from cryptocurrencies, the technology has been split to allow for diverse applications in many industrial fields.

For the internet dedicated to Blockchain and crypto trade, the technology must be made interoperable. Until then, the technology represents a threat to the economic system that has opened its doors to accept virtual currency, as long as people continue to mine it in unlawful and inefficient ways.

Adaptability

Many websites and software allow users to purchase and sell cryptocurrency, however, it is a peer-to-peer transaction. There isn't a single company or industry that accepts cryptocurrencies as payment for its services. Creating user-friendly mechanisms for purchasing, trading, storing, and using cryptocurrencies securely without being called out for it is a huge problem for the industry.

Price Dump

Even though the Bitcoin regulatory protocol was unaffected and that not a single Bitcoin was lost or stolen, people lost a lot of money. The demise of Bitcoin and examples of transnational failures are the main reasons why it came to an abrupt end in the first place. The trade and mining procedures in Bitcoin and other cryptocurrencies need to be regulated and changed urgently.

4. APPLICATIONS OF BLOCKCHAIN AND CRYPTOCURRENCY (KYC): [8,9]

KYC stands for "Know-Your-Customer", a term used during the customer identification process which is performed by the Banks and Financial Institutions while onboarding new customers. The main intention of conducting the KYC verification process is to determine identity and beneficial ownership of accounts, address of the customer, nature of customer's business lines, etc. This process ensures that Banks and Financial institutions' financial services are not misused by any customer. The KYC verification procedure is to be completed by the Banks before establishing any new financial operations/financial activities with its new or existing customers.

Banks must regularly update their customer details as per Government Instructions or Central Authority guidelines as a part of Customer Due Diligence policy.

4.1 Current KYC verification Process, Issues, and Challenges:

KYC verification process has become a mandatory part of Banks, Insures, and other Financial Institutions while onboarding new clients as a part of the Customer Identification Program (CIP). For the client who is planning to open an account in any financial institution or to get access to any financial services, the customer must visit the Bank in person and submit all the documents in physical form which will be safeguarded and stored by the Banks in their data warehouse or database systems. All stored information is shared with multiple agencies for the validation process on an individual basis. After a successful validation process, then all information is updated to Banks internal repository and each information will be reported to central agencies.

Assume, if the customer intends to get into a relationship with any other financial institutions or banks, then the same KYC verification procedure must be repeated by the Bank. For example, If the client needs to complete the KYC procedure to open a new Bank account, then he/she must submit approximately 10 documents. Say if the Bank has 1000 customers, then the data warehouse of the Bank will be filled up by 10000 documents, isn't it a space, time and cost consuming task...? now if the same documents have to be submitted to other Bank by the client to open new Bank account, then the tasks get replicated and again it consumes space, time and cost of the latter Bank to comply with KYC procedure.

Fig 2: KYC Current Verification Process

The current KYC processes are generally repetitive, time-consuming, leading to high administrative overhead costs and inconsistency.

- **Absence of single KYC system for multiple lines of business scenario and real-time data synchronization issues.**

Even though the customer's KYC-related information and documents are saved in the Bank's/Financial Institution's repository they are not in the position to transfer/pass on the same documents to the required Financial Institutions/Banks, on an average, it takes a maximum of 20 days to serve the purpose. For instance, in the case of a Letter of Credit.

- **Poor/Unsatisfactory customer experience.**

The client must submit the same documents multiple times in different Business scenarios which will lead to a painful experience for the client.

- **Inflexible Technology.**

Current repository systems are unable to adapt demands of changing regulatory requirements and few occasions they failed to provide efficient security assurance due to security breaches.

- **High operational cost while onboarding new clients.**

Bank experiences plenty of pain while onboarding new customers. Banks must spend an unwanted cost, effort, and mainly a lot of time while processing KYC verification. This process makes the Banks concentrate less on their core business working area.

According to a recent survey of Thomas Reuters revealed that Global financial organizations currently spend on the average cost of USD 60 million and some are spending up to USD 500 million every year to meet their obligations in terms of KYC and Customer Due Diligence(CDD) policies. This cost can be further augmented by the fines levied on Banks/Financial Institutions due to their misconduct with concern to anti-money-laundering and KYC regulations.

4.2 Blockchain as a solution and its Benefits:

By developing a permission-based KYC Blockchain network only trusted parties can involve in the KYC verification process. For example, When the customer submits the KYC documents such as passport copy, driving license copy, address proof, and other documents as proof to open a new bank account or to perform any new financial activities in Bank say Bank A, then Bank A verifies and stores it in the distributed ledgers and the customer will create a KYC ID after registering into the eKYC network. Now when the scenario is to open a new bank account or to apply for a loan in another Bank says Bank B, then the customer need not submit the same documents to Bank B again instead he can pass on the KYC ID to Bank B and the Bank B can retrieve the data from the distributed ledger which is already verified by Bank A. For all this process to happen the Bank B must join as the participant organization of the permission-based KYC network and must accept the endorsement policy of Bank A.

In KYC verification process using Blockchain technology can be implemented in two ways:

Intra Bank: The KYC verification process performed by the main Bank can be used by other Branches/Departments of the main Bank (In terms of the Para Bank scenario) which comes in the same jurisdiction to make the process hassle free and continuing the services to the client.

Inter Bank: Here Bank A acts as initiating Bank and performs an initial KYC Documents verification process for a client. When the client intends to access services of the Bank B then Bank B can access the already verified documents by Bank A from the KYC Blockchain network where Bank A and Bank B acts as a two-participant organizations of the Blockchain

network to establish trust and integrity in all verification and validation process. In this way, the KYC Blockchain network ensures secure inter-Bank documents exchange- enhancing process efficiency, standardizing KYC processes, and performing near-real-time client validations.

Fig 3: KYC verification process using Blockchain technology

5. CONCLUSION

Cryptocurrencies are built on blockchain technology, which is designed to create a trust mechanism in a peer-to-peer network based on the majority of nodes' consensus. This paper provides a brief overview of blockchain and cryptocurrencies, as well as the fundamentals of blockchain technology.

Despite the aforementioned obstacles, blockchain is progressing in the correct path toward widespread use of its services. As mentioned in several of the above explanations, the industry is aware of its issues and is attempting to resolve them. It'll only be a matter of time before these solutions are incorporated into the ecosystem, propelling blockchain into the mainstream.

After successful research work and study on Blockchain Technology and business operations of Banks/Financial Institutions, we concluded that implementation of eKYC Document Management System” using Blockchain technology will have a significant impact on KYC verification process while onboarding new customers.

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